

DISADVANTAGES OF TECHNOLOGICAL AUTOMATION IN METAL MELTING

Tolibayev Yerlan Amangeldiyevich

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Jienbaev Atabay Nietbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Dauletbayev Zamir Tangjarbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

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Abstract: Current scientific problems in the field of automation are considered in this article controlling the melting process of non-ferrous metals and electromagnetic levitation of potential solutions using modern digital technologies. The article describes the technological process of an electromagnet levitation smelting as a method of obtaining ultrapure metals and the main problems of automation this process, taking into account local and international experience. Prospective approaches monitoring the state of the solution in the inductor in real time based on vision systems is taken into account. The main problems and factors preventing the mass introduction of levitation melting. Emphasis is placed on industry in the electromagnetic field. Curie point crossing problem with a heated billet and the effect of the loss of the billet magnet on the oscillating circuit installation and inductor temperature are also taken into account. The main directions are also reflected in the article development of research in the field of levitation melting, including: optimization of energy costs, stabilization of the state of the solution in the inductor, predictable process control and scaling levitation melting units. concept of a digital twin based on a digital model as a component of automatic process control system to perform inductor control and forecasting technological parameters of the solution are presented. Ability to use vision for visual control based on video images to further stabilize the solution state in the inductor and improving the accuracy of numerical simulation results by showing the true geometry of the solution considered in parallel with the calculation of the model itself. The porosity of the powder the metallurgical component largely depends on the sintering temperature. Porosity variation of the powder in this study the fractional porosity of the metallurgical component in relation to its sintering temperature is studied the powder metallurgy component is obtained from the sintered density, and also the change in hardness is observed. is the same with respect to the sintering temperature.

Keywords: Automation, Hardness testing machine, numerical simulation, induction oven, Sintering temperature, levitation melting, vision system, vacuum oven, digital twin

Introduction

The metallurgical industry is one of the main sectors of the world economy. The demand for metal products has been growing steadily for several decades. The biggest one Consumers of construction, mechanical engineering and electronic industry industry. In addition to the increase in demand for non-ferrous and iron, the global trend moving toward lower greenhouse gas emissions and a smaller carbon footprint important factor. Current measures to regulate carbon policy also change the long-term perspective metals sector strategy. The above factors are driving leading steel companies to introduce new metal production and processing technologies, taking into account new energy costs and the environment. affects by ensuring a stable, uninterrupted supply of products in growing conditions Demand. The increased need for new materials makes it difficult for the metal industry to produce we can check the composition control of metals and alloys with improved technical characteristics. One of the tasks of metallurgy is the production of metals with a high degree of purity. This It is known that the properties of molten metal are usually determined by the concentration of impurities in its composition, which negatively affects the properties of the final material. Product quality can vary dramatically. Powder metallurgy is the art and science of producing metal powders and semi-finished products. and finished articles of individual, mixed or alloyed powders, whether or not non-metallic components. The production of powder metallurgy parts involves mixing elemental or alloy powders with additives. and lubricants, densifying the mixture in a suitable matrix and heating the resulting green compact under controlled conditions. an atmospheric furnace is used to bind metallurgical particles. The resulting parts are solid metal objects requires sufficient strength and density to be used in various fields. There are few errors in the results. Thus, it becomes important to avoid the formation of impurities in the resulting solution chemical reactions with the atmosphere and furnace walls, as well as melting crucible material components. In addition, to obtain a homogeneous material necessary to ensure uniform distribution of alloy components in the solution volume within a certain period of time (melting time). Among the various techniques for heating and melting metals, induction furnaces are widely used to provide non-contact control of melt mixing by electromagnetic field, temperature and surface shape. Instead of ordinary

ceramics crucible, induction furnace for electromagnetic processing of highly pure materials used with a cold crucible. Their application is the production of titanium photovoltaic cleaning of parts for the aerospace, automotive or medical industries and crystallization of silicon in semiconductor manufacturing. Because of the air gaps the cross-sectional metal crucible remains transparent to the electromagnetic field. Here's the pressure the effect of the electromagnetic field strongly compresses the solution, resulting in semi-levitation. The the solution falls to the bottom of a water-cooled crucible. Thus, contamination of the solution the crucible material is reduced. However, water-cooled crucibles and melts lose a lot of heat through contact regions appears to be the limiting factor for achieving high melting heats and is reflected in low energy efficiency of this process.

Picture 1. The inductor of the technological system. Cross-sectional view.

The temperature of the rising liquid metal can be measured using different pyrometers: color, radiation or optical. Only the last two types of pyrometers can be used conditions for liking the object of study. When measuring the temperature, there should be no impurities and oxides on the metal surface that disturb the temperature measurements. On the other hand, color pyrometers are not nearly as sensitive formation of films on glass; therefore, they are particularly suitable for such applications; although, they are very difficult to use and maintain. In the case of a glow pyrometer, the emission of metals must first be measured in a special device, because The principle of their operation is based on the detection of the emission of hot metal by temperature. Finding the dependence of the temperature on the emissivity of the sample for metals with high melting points, the absolute black body model is used. The the shape of the samples should be chosen in such a way that they have the greatest stability.

Balanced by the high energy costs of flotation high level of metal purification, but in any case they are important ratio of the cost of metal produced using this technology. An alternative method of non-contact metal melting is electromagnetic levitation melting Its distinctive feature is that the solution is suspended during the entire melting process and does not touch the surface of the crucible or the surface of the heating elements. The metal is kept suspended by the electromagnetic field produced in the inductor alternating current and induced current inside the needle, which is returned from the inductor According to Ampere's law. Special for electromagnetic melting of metal usually by levitation cone-shaped inductors with opposite current are used at the base of the cone. This is an inductor the design creates a so-called "potential pit" that traps the solution in an electromagnetic field from transverse vibration. Metal vacuum state currents produced by an inductor in a metal causing intense heating and subsequent melting. Induction melting of metals with full composition has two main advantages over ceramics or induction furnaces. First of all, the electromagnetic process in an inert atmosphere or the vacuum completely eliminates contamination of the solution with crucible materials and as a result, the purity of the solution is significantly improved. Secondly, as a result of heat loss of the liquid the metal is reduced and limited by radiation and evaporation, allowing electromagnetism field processing must be done at very high temperatures. Currently, metal melting in induction processes is used with significant limitations based on the solution mass conditions. This is because the mass of the solution increases the amount of energy required to suspend the metal increases significantly. First of all the use of non-contact metal melting is limited to the high-tech sector where it is required ultrapure metal, semiconductor manufacturing (especially single crystal silicon) and smelting, casting, alloying and refining of active metals such as scandium and their alloys; titanium, molybdenum, uranium, etc. There is also an electromagnetic levitation melting process for ferromagnetic metals some limitations related to changes in the properties of magnetic materials when heated. When a magnetic material is heated to the Curie point, it loses its magnetic properties, causing the inductor to overheat and introduce unwanted sample vibrations and in a crucible, this process takes place quickly.

Conclusions

The presented review presents the current state of metal melting in the technological system electromagnetic field is described. Comprehensive automation and adaptation to it mass introduction into industry is described.

Analysis of the most pressing problems It was determined in the process of scientific investigation, in particular, from the point of view energy saving. Current scientific research in the field of metal smelting technologies will be reviewed useful information for researchers working in related fields. The following the problems were identified as proposed solutions to these scientific questions:

Development of a vision system to monitor the condition of the molten sample on the inductor and monitoring its surface temperature based on deep ultra-precision neural network trained on synthetic data;

Development of a simulation model for heating and melting in an electromagnetic ferromagnetic metal workpiece area and Curie point tracking system reflected in the transit (digital twin) process based on a simulation model calculated in real time;

Development of an electromagnetic process system to suspend the solution for cooling and crystallization when the power inductor is turned off.

Further research in the field of technological smelting of metals increasing the mass of melting furnaces and molten metal, as well as optimization consumption of electric furnaces consists in reducing the consumption of energy. In addition, it is a promising direction of research solving the problem of stabilizing the state of the sample in the inductor. Such as we intend to develop a framework for further work within this research enables computer vision-based monitoring of the state of the molten sample in the inductor. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, gave several examples of the processes of their application in mining and presented to international journals the methods of automation of mining technologies through microprocessors and the technologies in mining at the same time. proved with several examples that it can be used in several technological processes. The use of modern technologies plays an important role in the development economy of the mine. It is necessary to pay attention to the parameters of technologies when automating processes in mining enterprises. Do not set the load beyond the limits of the technology, only then the technology will work for a long time without problems. In this article, I will inform you that if we install a microprocessor (automatic mode memory) in the technology in the mining enterprises, we will prevent the overloading of the technology. This ensures the operation of the enterprise and the safety of workers. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, has articles on metallurgical processes, components of

metals, and metal enrichment processes. Much research has been done on the metallurgical industry. A number of information on processes in metallurgical deposits, extraction of metals, corrosion of metals and extraction of metals by flotation methods are presented.

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